

SEARCH FOR INSECTICIDES. PART I

BY A. B. SEN AND P. M. BHARGAVA

Preparation of certain trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-halogenated phenylethanes and halogenated phenyl esters of trichloroacetic acid has been described.

Two theories have been put forward concerning the remarkable insecticidal powers of dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (Busvine, *Nature*, 1945, 156, 169). One postulates that toxic component is the linked *p*-chlorobenzene rings, while the chloroformic residue $-CCl_3$ imparts lipoid solubility (Läuger, Martin and Müller, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 892). According to the other theory, the lipoid solubility is attributed to the chlorobenzene rings, while the remainder of the molecule is supposed to be responsible for toxicity, by splitting off HCl at the vital centres (Martin and Wain, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 512).

In this paper, two types of reactions have been carried out in order to introduce a toxic and a lipoid soluble group in the molecule, with a view to studying the effect of these different groups on insecticidal action.

The first is the condensation of chloral with the Grignard reagents of polyhalogenated benzenes. Condensation of chloral with Grignard reagents of *p*-chlorobromobenzene, *o*-chlorobromobenzene and 1:2-dichloro-4-bromobenzene yields 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane, 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(2-chlorophenyl)ethane and 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(3:4-dichlorophenyl)ethane respectively. Of these compounds, the first [*i. e.* 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane] has been obtained previously, as a by-product in the manufacture of DDT (Forest, Stephenson and Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 333). According to them, the compound is contained in the lower boiling fraction (b. p. 115°/0.5 mm.) which is obtained as a by-product in the technical preparation of DDT, and that the compound yields an acetyl derivative which on hydrolysis regenerates the original hydroxy compound as a solid. The present authors have obtained 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane as a viscous liquid, b. p. 196°-198°/11 mm. It yields an acetyl derivative which is not hydrolysed by *N*/2-sulphuric acid. 1:1:1-Trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(2-chlorophenyl)ethane also yields an acetyl derivative, but the acetyl derivative of 1:1:1-trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(3:4-dichlorophenyl)ethane could not be obtained.

It has been incidentally found that the bromination of chlorobenzene in CCl_4 solution, in the presence of Al-Hg couple, results in the formation of *p*-chlorobromobenzene in a good yield, whereas if the same reaction is carried out without a solvent, the reaction is much more vigorous and the product formed is mainly the isomeric *o*-chlorobromobenzene.

Another series of compounds, which have been prepared, is of the type of esters. These have been obtained by the condensation of the sodium salts of *p*-chlorophenol, 2:4-dichlorophenol and 2:4:6-trichlorophenol with trichloroacetyl chloride. *p*-Chlorophenol gives a theoretical yield of the trichloroacetyl ester (I). 2:4-Dichlorophenol, which has

one *ortho* position occupied by chlorine, gives a 55% yield of the ester (II), while in the case of 2:4:6-trichlorophenol, which has both the *ortho* positions substituted, the yield of the trichloroacetyl ester (III) is very low (5.4%).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

p-Chlorobromobenzene was obtained by Korner previously by the bromination of chlorobenzene (*Gazzetta*, 1874, 4, 342; "Jahresbericht über die Fortschritte der Chemie," 1875, p. 319), but the exact experimental details not being available it was prepared by the authors in the following way.

The bromination was carried out in a 500 c. c. welded-neck flask, fitted with a dropping funnel and a reflux condenser, connected at the top to a gas absorption trap. Chlorobenzene (40 g.), diluted with an equal volume of CCl_4 , was taken in the flask, and a little freshly prepared Al-Hg couple added to it. Bromine (20 c. c.) was then added dropwise through the dropping funnel, in the course of 1½ hours, the flask being surrounded by ice-water, and the contents of the flask were left at room temperature overnight. Next day, on diluting with alcohol (100 c. c.), orange-yellow plates of *para*-chlorobromobenzene separated out. The crystals were filtered off at the pump. On removing the alcohol from the filtrate and cooling, another crop of the compound was obtained, yield 40 g. (59% of theory), m. p. 66°.

1:1-Trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane.—The Grignard reagent was prepared by adding *p*-chlorobromobenzene (17 g.), dissolved in ether, to magnesium (2.3 g.) suspended in ether (50 c. c.), under continuous stirring by a mechanical stirrer in an atmosphere of nitrogen, and refluxing for about 2 hours. The dark coloured solution was then cooled in ice and chloral (13 g.), diluted with an equal volume of ether, added to it drop by drop during the course of an hour, when a yellow product separated out. The mixture was then refluxed for an hour, the Grignard complex acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and then transferred to a separating funnel. The deep yellow, emulsion-like ethereal layer was separated, washed with sulphuric acid and then with water till free from acid. It was left in a refrigerator for 48 hours and then filtered. A yellowish residue (1 g.) which did not melt and which was insoluble in ether, was left and could not be identified. The filtrate was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off on a water-bath, final traces being removed at the water pump. The residual liquid was then distilled in vacuum on a metal bath, when a bright yellow, very viscous liquid was obtained at 194°-198°/11 mm. The liquid possesses a characteristic smell and reacts with sodium, yield 13 g. (55% of theory). (Found: C, 36.66; H, 2.28; Cl, 54.29. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{OCl}_3$ requires C, 36.92; H, 2.31; Cl, 54.61 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* of the above was prepared by boiling the hydroxy compound with acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate for 5 minutes, and then allowing it to cool. The mixture was then diluted with water and boiled to decompose the excess of acetic anhydride. On cooling, the acetyl derivative was precipitated (theoretical yield). Recrystallised from dilute acetic acid, it was obtained as fine, white needles, m. p. 118-19° (Found: C, 39.31; H, 2.62. $C_{10}H_8O_2Cl_4$ requires C, 39.73; H, 2.65 per cent).

o-Chlorobromobenzene.—Bromination of chlorobenzene (15 g.) was carried out in the same way as in the preparation of the *p*-isomer, excepting that the chlorobenzene was not diluted with CCl_4 . The reaction was much more vigorous. After the addition of bromine, the mixture was left for a week for the completion of the reaction, then treated with a solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove HBr and Br_2 , and the oil separating was taken up with ether. The ethereal extract was filtered and the filtrate left for evaporation of the ether at the room temperature. The residual oil was distilled under ordinary pressure, when at 196°-200° a colourless liquid was obtained. This on cooling in ice deposited a few crystals of *p*-chlorobromobenzene. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and redistilled, b. p. 196°-199°, yield 14.5 g. (58% of theory). (Found: C, 37.97; H, 2.07. Calc for C_6H_4ClBr : C, 38.12; H, 2.14 per cent).

1:1:1-Trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(2-chlorophenyl)ethane.—The Grignard reagent was prepared by adding *o*-chlorobromobenzene (12.8 g.) in ethereal solution to magnesium (2.2 g.), suspended in ether (50 c.c.), under continuous stirring by a mechanical stirrer in an atmosphere of nitrogen, and refluxing for about 4 hours. The dark coloured solution was then cooled in ice, and chloral (9.9 g.), diluted with an equal volume of ether was added drop by drop during the course of an hour; it was then worked up in a similar manner as with the *-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane* analogue. An insoluble residue, which did not melt, was obtained in this experiment also. The filtered ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off on a water-bath. The residual liquid was distilled in vacuum on a metal-bath, when a brilliant red, viscous liquid collected in the receiver at 196°-198°/7mm. The liquid possesses a characteristic smell and reacts vigorously with sodium, yield 8 g. (46% of theory). (Found: C, 36.49; H, 2.07; Cl, 54.91. $C_8H_6OCl_3$ requires C, 36.92; H, 2.31; Cl, 54.61 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* of the above compound was prepared in the usual way (theoretical yield). Recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid gave a colourless crystalline compound, m. p. 96-97°. (Found: C, 39.25; H, 2.72. $C_{10}H_8O_2Cl_4$ requires C, 39.73; H, 2.75 per cent).

1:1:1-Trichloro-2-hydroxy-2-(3:4-dichlorophenyl)ethane.—The Grignard reagent of 1:2-dichloro-4-bromobenzene (18.5 g., b. p. 124°/33mm.) with Mg (2.3 g.) was prepared in a similar way as described in the preceding compound with about 6 hours' refluxing. The solution was then cooled in ice and reacted with chloral (13.5 g.), and the yellow mixture was then refluxed for an hour; the Grignard reagent was then decomposed and extracted as in the case of *-2-(4-chlorophenyl)ethane*. The ethereal extract after washing was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the ether distilled off,

final traces being removed on a water pump. The residual liquid was then distilled in vacuum on a water-bath, when a bright orange-red liquid was obtained at 55° - $57^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$ It solidified on cooling in ice to a red crystalline solid, having a characteristic smell and reacting vigorously with sodium, yield 10 g. (42% of theory). (Found: C, 32.20; H, 1.82; Cl, 59.93. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OCl}_3$ requires C, 32.70; H, 1.70; Cl, 60.27 per cent). The colour of the liquid faded on keeping and in the course of a few months it disappeared completely, a crystalline colourless solid being then obtained on cooling in ice.

Trichloroacetate of p-Chlorophenol.—The sodium salt of *p*-chlorophenol was prepared by adding a little less than the required amount of caustic soda, dissolved in a small quantity of water, to the phenol, using phenolphthalein as the indicator. The solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and left in a vacuum desiccator.

The sodium salt of *p*-chlorophenol (7.5 g.) was suspended in petrol ether (50 c.c.) in a pyrex flask fitted with a reflux condenser and trichloroacetyl chloride (10.5 g., slight excess over the required amount) was added. A vigorous reaction with brisk effervescence ensued. After the reaction had subsided, the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for $\frac{3}{4}$ hour, when the petrol ether layer assumed a dark green colour, with the separation of sodium chloride. The reaction mixture was cooled and then filtered. The petrol ether was distilled off from the filtrate on a water-bath, final traces of the solvent being removed on a water pump. The residual liquid was then distilled in vacuum on an oil-bath, when a colourless liquid, b. p. 94° - $98^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, was obtained, yield theoretical. The liquid possesses a characteristic smell and darkens on keeping. (Found: C, 34.81; H, 1.66; Cl, 51.52. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_3$ requires C, 35.03; H, 1.46; Cl, 51.82 per cent).

The ester on hydrolysis with 20% alcoholic potash regenerated *p*-chlorophenol and trichloroacetic acid. The hydrolysis was carried out by refluxing for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours the ester (2 g.) with 20% alcoholic potash (30 c.c.) to which water (2 c.c.) was added. After hydrolysis, the alcohol was removed by distillation, the residue was cooled in ice and then acidified with 18% hydrochloric acid, when crystals of trichloroacetic acid separated out and *p*-chlorophenol was obtained as a red oil forming a layer. The chlorophenol was separated by extraction with ether; the ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, and the phenol then identified after distillation, b. p. 215° .

Trichloroacetate of 2:4-Dichlorophenol.—The dry sodium salt of dichlorophenol (10.2 g.), prepared in the same way as in the previous experiment, was suspended in petrol ether (50 c. c.) and trichloroacetyl chloride (20 g., approximately double the theoretical amount) added to it. After the vigour of the reaction had subsided, the mixture was refluxed for $\frac{3}{4}$ hour, cooled and then filtered. The filtrate was washed with 1% caustic soda solution, and then with water till free from alkali. It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the petrol ether distilled off on a water-bath. Trichloroacetyl chloride and last traces of the solvent were removed on a water pump and the residual liquid distilled in vacuum on a metal bath. The first fraction (boiling between 80° and $130^{\circ}/0.5\text{ mm.}$) consisted mainly of the unchanged dichlorophenol (4 g. approximately) which solidified in the receiver, and was collected separately. The ester distilled at $162^{\circ}/0.5\text{ mm.}$ or $167^{\circ}/3\text{ mm.}$ as a colourless liquid which did not solidify in the receiver. The liquid possesses a pungent smell and acquires a dark brown colour in course of time, yield 8.4 g. (55% of theory),

(Found: C, 31.22; H, 1.11; Cl, 57.99. $C_3H_3O_2Cl_3$ requires C, 31.44; H, 0.97; Cl, 57.54 per cent).

Trichloroacetate of 2:4:6-Trichlorophenol.—The sodium salt of 2:4:6-trichlorophenol was prepared in the same way as the sodium salt of *p*-chlorophenol. Trichloroacetyl chloride (10 g., approximately double the theoretical amount) was then added to dry sodium salt of the trichlorophenol (12 g.) in petrol ether. The mixture was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and left overnight. It was then filtered and solvent distilled off. Trichloroacetyl chloride and the last traces of the solvent were removed on a water pump. The residual liquid was then distilled in vacuum on a metal-bath, when at $83^\circ/1$ mm., the unchanged trichlorophenol collected and solidified in the receiver. About 85% of the trichlorophenol was thus recovered back. After no more of the phenol distilled, the residue in the Claisen flask was washed several times with 2% sodium hydroxide solution. The insoluble portion, covered with the alkali solution, was left in a refrigerator and filtered the next day. The residue was washed with about 20 c.c. of petrol ether and then dried. The ester was thus obtained as a dull, white, crystalline solid, m. p. 189° , yield 1.2 g. (5.4% of theory). (Found: C, 27.47; H, 0.70. $C_6H_3O_2Cl_3$ requires C, 28.0; H, 0.58 per cent).

The insecticidal action and some physical properties of the compounds, described above, are under investigation.

One of the authors (P. M. B.) is indebted to the Lucknow University for the award of a research grant, and to the U. P. Government for the award of a research scholarship for continuing this work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY.

Received March 22, 1948.